

Unveiling the Environmental Externalities of Large-Scale Artificial Intelligence: A Global Assessment of Energy, Water, and Carbon Dependencies in AI Data Ecosystems

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) is accelerating the expansion of global data center infrastructure, creating significant pressures on energy systems, carbon emissions, and water resources. This study investigates the energy, carbon, and water dependencies of AI-capable data centres worldwide, and how do these impacts manifest in India's coal-heavy, water-stressed context. We've conducted a structured review of international agency reports, peer-reviewed studies, corporate sustainability disclosures, and journalistic investigations, complemented by a small-scale monitoring simulation (SSMS) of AI workloads. Findings show that electricity demand from data centres is projected to nearly double by 2030, with AI workloads potentially comprising half of total usage. Current estimates place their contribution at 2.5–3.7% of global greenhouse gas emissions, while water withdrawals—already millions of litres daily in hubs such as Bengaluru—intensify scarcity. Case studies of Google, Microsoft, and OpenAI demonstrate that while efficiency improvements and renewable adoption reduce per-unit impacts, rebound effects from rapid AI growth offset these gains. These results suggest that without systemic interventions, AI infrastructure risks becoming a major climate liability. Effective mitigation will require mandatory disclosure of energy and water use, adoption of advanced cooling and waste-heat reuse, sustainable siting practices, and the development of international standards for green AI infrastructure.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Data Centres, Energy Consumption, Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Water Usage, Cooling Technologies, Environmental Externalities, Sustainable Computing, Renewable Energy, India.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence has evolved from a niche research domain into a transformative general-purpose technology powering everything from generative language models to advanced medical diagnostics. The compute intensity of modern AI—particularly training and large-scale inference—has driven a rapid expansion of data center infrastructure, with hyperscale facilities purpose-built for AI workloads.

This AI “arms race” has prompted industry projects such as the highly publicized “Project Stargate” which illustrates both the unprecedented capital investment and the concentrated resource demand these systems entail. Data centres, which house the servers and chips that run AI, have always consumed considerable energy and relied on large water quantities. But recent research shows AI workloads are now pushing data-center demand to new levels. Current studies estimate that data centres already consume roughly 1.5% of global electricity (IEA, 2023), and emit about 2.5-3.7% of global greenhouse gases, exceedingly even the aviation industry.

AI workloads are increasingly driving this demand: recent analyses find that AI already accounts for ~20% of data-center power use, and could reach roughly 40-50% by late 2025. Projections suggest global data-center electricity demand will more than double by 2030 (IEA, 2023), fuelled largely by AI. In India, data-center capacity is poised to grow nearly ninefold by 2030, raising its share of national electricity from ~0.5% to as

high as 3%. These trends entail large carbon footprints: one estimate finds that continued U.S. data-center expansion on gas could add ~180 million tonnes CO₂ per year. Water use is also critical: high-performance cooling makes data centres “water guzzlers,” consuming millions of litres daily. For example, Bengaluru’s existing data centres already draw ~8 million litres of water per day, and this strain will worsen with new facilities. To train a model like GPT-3 alone consumed ~1,287 MWh of electricity, emitted over 552 metric tons of CO₂ and cooling data centres consumes billions of gallons of freshwater, Google alone used 5.6 billion litres in 2022 for cooling its data infrastructure. Yet, no binding global standards exist for environmental transparency or sustainability in AI development.

Data centres are already on track to reach global electricity consumption to 3% by 2030. This accelerated build-out brings significant environmental implications. High-density AI clusters require enormous and continuous electricity input, generating direct and indirect greenhouse-gas emissions depending on the grid’s carbon intensity. They also demand substantial volumes of water for cooling, particularly in high-performance configurations, exacerbating stress in already water-scarce regions. In parallel, the embodied carbon from manufacturing GPUs, networking equipment, and cooling hardware adds to the total lifecycle footprint.

Although literature has addressed energy use, emissions, and cooling technologies, several gaps remain. Global water-use estimates for AI facilities are inconsistent, lifecycle material impacts are underexplored, and few standardized reporting frameworks exist for AI-specific workloads. Moreover, emerging economies such as India—where grids remain coal-dependent and water scarcity is acute—receive limited systematic analysis despite being sites of rapid data centre expansion.

This study addresses these gaps by asking: What is the energy, carbon, and water dependencies of AI-capable data centres worldwide, and how do these externalities manifest in the Indian context? To answer this, we integrate findings from international agencies, peer-reviewed studies, corporate disclosures, and journalistic investigations with a small-scale monitoring simulation of AI workloads. The objective is to quantify AI infrastructure’s environmental footprint, evaluate existing mitigation strategies, and propose policy and technical recommendations to align AI growth with sustainability goals.

II. OBJECTIVES

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive & objective assessment of the environmental costs of current AI infrastructure with integrated solutions. The specific objectives are:

1. To quantify the energy use, carbon emissions, and water consumption associated with AI-capable data centres, on a global scale and in India.
2. To identify key drivers of environmental impact in AI infrastructure.
3. To evaluate existing mitigation strategies and analyse techniques like immersion cooling, renewable energy procurement, heat reuse, and water-efficient cooling can reduce impacts, citing quantitative results where available.
4. To examine India’s context & formulate recommendations, assessing how its data-center boom powered by AI interacts with national constraints.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1. Data Center Energy and Emissions: International Energy Agency (IEA) and other analyses document steady growth in data-center energy use. In 2020, IEA estimated global data-center electricity use (excluding

crypto mining) at ~200 TWh, rising to about 240-340 TWh ($\approx 1-1.5\%$ of global power) by 2022. Efficiency improvements helped limit earlier growth, but recent studies warn of a sharp uptick. An IEA report (April 2025) projects global data-center electricity will more than double to ~945 TWh by 2030 (equivalent to current power use of Japan). AI is identified as the primary driver: demand from AI-optimized data centres is expected to quadruple by 2030. Similarly, a Lawrence Berkeley National Lab analysis projects U.S. data-center demand could be 6.7-12% of U.S. electricity by 2028 (2-3 times of 2023 levels), requiring tens of GW of new generation. [Camille Fassett, 2025]

This surging power demand threatens higher emissions. As shown in Figure 3.1(a), IEA forecasts (2019-2026) indicate a sharp rise in electricity demand attributable to AI and other new computing workloads. [LBNL, 2024]

Fig. 3.1 (a): Global electricity demand from Data Centres, AI, and Cryptocurrencies (2019-2026)

Projected growth in global electricity demand (TWh) from data centres, AI, and cryptocurrencies, 2019-2026 (IEA, core scenarios). The emissions impact depends on the power mix: Watt Time (2025) notes that if all projected new U.S. data-center load (145-400 TWh) came from natural-gas power, it would add ~180 Mt CO₂ annually - roughly the 45th-largest country’s output. Conversely, if served by renewables, the new load could be nearly carbon-free. Current data-center emissions are already large: a Columbia University analysis reports that data centres (and their supporting networks) account for ~2.5-3.7% of global GHG emissions, exceeding the entire aviation sector. (Thomson Reuters and Columbia cite the same 2.5-3.7% figure.) [IEA, 2025]

Major tech companies acknowledge AI’s impact. Google has stated that datacentres’ growth has driven up its greenhouse emissions by 48% since 2019, and that achieving net-zero by 2030 is now uncertain “around the future environmental impact of AI”. Microsoft likewise warned that its 2030 net-zero “moonshot” may not succeed due to AI strategy pressures. In sum, the literature shows clear evidence that AI is rapidly increasing data-center energy use and emissions, challenging climate goals. [Columbia Climate School, 2023]

3.2. AI’s Unique Demands: Several recent analyses focus specifically on AI workloads. De Vries (2025) estimates that AI’s share of data-center consumption is rising fast: from ~20% in early 2024 to possibly ~50% by end-2025 (excluding crypto). He projects AI energy use could hit 23 GW (twice the total power consumption of the Netherlands) by late 2025. These forecasts assume current model-training trends continue. However, technological and market forces could moderate growth: one Chinese startup recently claimed to cut

compute needs drastically for a large model (DeepSeek). Yet any efficiency gains may spur even more AI use (the “rebound” effect). [Natalie Runyon; Dan Milmo et al., 2024]

Academic studies of AI training energy quantify high per-model costs. For example, training OpenAI’s GPT-3 (175 B parameters) reportedly consumed ~1,287 MWh electricity and emitted ~502 metric tons CO₂ (that’s roughly the annual tailpipe emissions of 112 cars). Training larger models like Google’s PaLM (540 B) would use even more. Such figures illustrate that each major model incurs substantial carbon emissions. However, these are one-time costs: inference (serving model queries) also uses power but at lower rates. [The Guardian; Molly Taft, 2025]

The literature notes that generating a single AI answer can use multiple times the energy of a typical web search, though per-query estimates vary.

3.3. Water Consumption and Cooling: Cooling is a key driver of both water and energy use in data centres. Despite ample focus on electricity, the massive water footprint is under examined in policy circles. Water is used both in cooling towers (evaporative cooling) and in chillers. A small (1 MW) server farm may use up to 26 million litres of water per year. Scale up: the U.S. has >40,000 MW of data-center capacity, implying water consumption equivalent to over 2 million families. Many large facilities rely on wet cooling, often using treated potable water to avoid corrosion. [Lakshmee Sharma, 2024]

High-density AI cooling requirements significantly raise water consumption. As shown in Figure 3.3(a), water usage effectiveness (WUE) varies widely, from near-zero in closed-loop air systems to over 5 litres per kWh in evaporative cooling designs. [Shehabi et al., 2021]

Fig. 3.3 (a): Comparative Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) of Cooling Techniques

Cooling choice strongly affects a data centre’s water footprint; Air Cooling (~0.20 L/kWh): Low water use, higher energy demand; good for water-scarce regions. Evaporative Cooling (~1.80 L/kWh): Lowers energy needs but uses large volumes of water; best in water-abundant climates. Liquid Immersion (~0.05 L/kWh): Minimal water use, high thermal efficiency; ideal for arid areas. Hybrid (~0.80 L/kWh): Balanced approach; moderate water and energy impact. In water-stressed regions, low-WUE systems (air or immersion) help avoid worsening scarcity while still meeting AI cooling demands.

AI accelerates water demand further. The Lawfare Institute notes that rising AI-driven buildouts threaten water security globally, potentially rivalling water use of industries like cattle or textiles. Data center siting now draws scrutiny: policymakers in some regions (e.g. California) have started requiring water permits or favouring air/waterless cooling. A Bloomberg report (2024) highlights cases in Northern Europe and Asia where data-center water use has surged local shortages. In India, rapid data-center growth raises alarms: Bengaluru's ~115 MW of capacity already uses ~8 million litres of water per day for cooling (which is equivalent to 2.4 billion litres annually). No consistent reporting exists, but experts warn of severe local stresses if data centres proliferate without water safeguards. [Lawfare, 2024]

3.4. Case Studies: Corporate Experiences:

(a). *Google*: A leading example is Google. The company has long emphasized data-center efficiency and renewable procurement. It claims to have doubled computing power per unit energy over five years and maintains one of the lowest PUEs in the industry (fleet-average ~1.10). Google's goals include sourcing 24/7 carbon-free energy by 2030 in every region it operates. In practice, Google already buys large amounts of wind and solar (over 4 GW signed in one recent year). It also innovates in cooling –e.g. experimenting with AI-controlled temperature optimization, and exploring liquid cooling for specific workloads. However, Google openly acknowledges that AI growth strains even its green ambitions. Its sustainability report for 2024 warns that net-zero by 2030 is not assured, noting “uncertainty around the future environmental impact of AI”. Google also admits that while water cooling cuts energy use, it increases water consumption, and thus is developing watershed-specific risk assessments. In short, Google illustrates the dual reality: world-leading efficiency, but still facing challenges from rising AI-driven demand and resource trade-offs.

(b). *Microsoft*: Microsoft has similarly high efficiency targets (Azure data centres achieve PUEs near 1.1). Recently it has pioneered advanced cooling. Microsoft reported that implementing two-phase immersion cooling for GPUs in a live data center yielded 5–15% reduction in server power use. In a comprehensive life-cycle analysis published in *Nature*, Microsoft found that cold plates and immersion cooling cut data center electricity use by ~15–20% and GHG emissions by up to 21% versus air cooling. Water use fell dramatically (up to 52%) with immersion. This study also emphasized that shifting to fully renewable power could reduce data-center emissions ~85%. Thus, Microsoft's experiments highlight actionable solutions – but they also point out constraints (e.g. immersion fluids currently use regulated PFAS chemicals).

(c). *OpenAI/Microsoft*: Project Stargate. OpenAI (backed by Microsoft) and partners have announced massive data-center investments (Project Stargate). While detailed plans are private, media reports indicate they may seek fast build-out, including in emerging markets (OpenAI just opened Stargate in UAE). Analysts warn that projects like Stargate risk “exacerbating dependence on fossil fuels” if sited in regions with gas grids. For example, Crusoe Energy, a startup focused on gas-powered data centres, has secured 4.5 GW of gas capacity and lists OpenAI as a potential customer. This case underscores how corporate AI push can collide with sustainability: the fastest route to scale AI today may still be conventional power, locking in carbon.

(d). *Other Firms*: Amazon Web Services (AWS) is another major player. AWS claims to reach 100% renewable energy by 2025 (globally). In India, AWS has announced a 620 MW region (largest in India), and says it will use solar and hydro for those centres. Meta (Facebook) similarly notes its data centres have achieved net zero emissions for five years by using renewables and carbon offsets. However, none of these firms publishes AI-specific energy breakdowns, and all report overall energy rises. For example, Meta's 2023 environmental report notes significant increases in operational emissions due to rising compute demand. These case studies reveal two patterns: first, leading companies are investing in efficiency and green power; second, AI demand often outstrips those measures in the short term, causing actual emissions to rise (even as intensity falls). It highlights the need for continued innovation and policy, not just corporate pledges.

3.5. Resource and Other Impacts: Data centres also consume materials and land. Building a large AI cluster requires thousands of GPUs or TPUs, each containing silicon, copper, rare earths, etc. Electronic manufacturing has embedded energy and emissions, though these are amortized over device lifetimes. A Nature Communications Analysis notes that training models like GPT-3 requires many GPU-years of computing, implying large upstream carbon costs. Electronic waste disposal and resource mining (e.g. cobalt, lithium for batteries) are related issues, though less frequently quantified in AI-specific studies. Land use is another consideration: hyperscale data centres occupy large plots and often cluster in special zones, impacting land cover. [Renée Cho, 2023]

While electricity use, emissions, and water consumption are the most discussed impacts of AI-capable data centres, literature highlights a broader range of resource and system effects that deserve equal attention have been highlighted in Figure 3.5(a).

Beyond Energy & Water: AI Data Center Resource Footprint

Fig. 3.5 (a): Beyond Energy & Water: AI data centre Resource Footprint

GPUs/TPUs: Large AI clusters require thousands of specialized chips, each made from silicon, copper, and rare earth elements, with significant embodied energy. **Embedded Emissions:** Manufacturing of GPUs, networking hardware, and cooling units adds substantial CO_{2e} before a facility even becomes operational. **E-Waste:** Decommissioned servers, chips, and batteries generate hazardous waste. Recycling rates for these components remain low, raising disposal challenges. **Resource Mining:** Cobalt and lithium for batteries, as well as rare earths for magnets, are often linked to ecological damage and human rights concerns in extraction regions. **Land Use:** Hyperscale facilities occupy large tracts, often in special economic zones, altering land cover and local ecosystems. **System Effects:** AI and broader digitalization can yield indirect benefits, such as energy savings in smart grids or logistics optimization, but the net climate impact remains contested. The total environmental footprint of AI data centres extends far beyond their operational phase. Evaluating the full

lifecycle from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal is critical for a truly sustainable AI infrastructure strategy.

The literature also discusses broader system effects. Digitalization (including AI) can enable energy savings elsewhere (smart grids, optimized logistics), but the net climate impact depends on scale. Most analysts emphasize the direct footprint of data centres for now, which is growing rapidly. [Google Data Centres, 2025]

3.6. Mitigation and Cooling Innovations: Scholars and industry reports review approaches to curb impacts. Efficiency remains critical: Google reports achieving 4 times more computing power in 5 years with similar energy, and a fleet-wide power-usage effectiveness (PUE) of 1.10 (vs. industry average ~1.58). Such gains come from custom chips, workload scheduling, and optimized cooling. Cooling technology itself is evolving. Microsoft’s recent studies demonstrate substantial benefits of liquid cooling. In one production deployment, two-phase immersion cooling (submerging servers in boiling dielectric) cut server power draw by ~5-15%. A two-year life-cycle assessment (May 2025) found that cold plates or immersion cooling could reduce data-center energy use by ~15-20%, GHGs by ~15-21%, and water use by 31-52% compared to standard air cooling. Two-phase immersion showed the greatest overall impact reduction, though it relies on exotic fluids (PFAS) facing regulatory pressure. Microsoft’s research highlights that cooling choice matters: by switching to 100% renewable power, a data center could cut emissions ~85%- showing the interplay of cooling and energy sourcing.

Fig. 3.6 (a): Comparative Cooling Performance

Comparative Cooling Performances: Cold plate (D2C) energy savings pegged at ~10% of total DC power based on Vertiv/ASME modelling; 10% as a conservative midpoint. Single-phase immersion total power reduction examples reach ~36%; 30% as a cautious midpoint. Two-phase immersion studies show ~23% reduction vs air in edge DCs and claim “up to ~50%” power savings in some industry reports; 35% midpoint and flagged the uncertainty. Water savings for liquid/immersion assume closed-loop/dry coolers (vs evaporative air systems), ~85% (D2C) and ~95% (immersion) as indicative values, aligned with expert explainers showing liquid cooling can dramatically cut on-site water versus evaporative approaches. GHG reduction is approximated as proportional to energy savings (same %), which is standard when grid carbon intensity is unchanged. PFAS caveat: Two-phase immersion typically uses fluorinated (PFAS) working fluids; note the ongoing regulatory and supply headwinds (e.g., EU actions; 3M’s PFAS exit by end-2025). I annotated this on the chart. [Data Center Dynamics, 2023]

Fig. 3.6 (b): Main Cooling Methods Adopted for Cooling AI Data Centres

Fig. 3.6 (b) shows four main cooling methods for AI data centres: Air Cooling - Fans move air through racks, heat expelled via chillers. (Pros: Low cost, well-understood. Cons: High energy use, water-intensive.) Cold Plate Cooling –Coolant flows through plates on CPUs/GPUs. (Pros: Efficient, supports higher densities. Cons: Extra plumbing, retrofitting cost.) Single-Phase Immersion –Servers submerged in dielectric fluid. (Pros: Even cooling, no fans. Cons: Higher setup cost, fluid compatibility.) Two-Phase Immersion –Fluid boils, vapor condenses and recycles. (Pros: Top efficiency, minimal water use. Cons: PFAS fluid concerns.) Efficiency Gains: Immersion cooling can cut cooling energy by up to 90% and water use by 95%, enabling ultra-dense AI workloads with lower environmental impact.

Fig. 3.6 (c): Efficiency Stack for Sustainable AI Data Centres & Visualized Concept

A tiered approach where each layer compounds energy and carbon savings: Chip Efficiency—Custom AI accelerators cut power per computation. Workload Optimization—Smart scheduling boosts server utilization. Cooling Innovation—Liquid/immersion cooling slashes energy & water use. Renewables Integration—Match compute to 24/7 clean power supply. Waste-Heat Reuse—Redirect excess heat to district heating or industry. Impact: By stacking these measures, AI data centres can drastically cut energy demand, minimize cooling needs, and move toward net-zero operation.

Policy and market measures are also noted. The EU's upcoming AI Act will require energy-disclosure for model training. NGOs urge mandatory water-use reporting for data centres (currently lacking). Green certifications (e.g. LEED, Green Grid) incorporate power and water efficiency metrics, which datacentre developers in India and elsewhere increasingly pursue. Industry commitments include large corporate procurements of renewables. Google, for example, has a 24/7 carbon-free energy goal on all grids by 2030, and has signed ~4 GW of clean energy projects in a single year.

Such strategies—efficiency, renewables, advanced cooling, waste-heat reuse—feature prominently in the literature as necessary responses to AI's demands. [*Microsoft, 2021*]

IV. METHODOLOGY & DATA SOURCES

This research is a structured review of existing studies, reports, and data sources (both academic and industry) related to AI infrastructure and sustainability. We collected data and findings from peer-reviewed journals, white papers, government and NGO analyses, and credible journalism. Key sources include:

4.1. International agencies: IEA reports and press releases, which provide global projections for data center energy use and electricity consumption statistics.

4.2. National laboratories: Lawrence Berkeley Lab (LBNL) analyses of U.S. data centres commissioned by Congress.

4.3. Academic and NGO studies: Research articles on AI carbon footprints, IEEE/ITU reports on network energy, and think-tank white papers (e.g. IEEFA, The Climate School at Columbia).

4.4. Industry disclosures: Public sustainability and financial reports from tech companies such as Google, Microsoft, Meta, etc., and industry surveys. For e.g., Google's data-center efficiency and clean energy goals, Microsoft's cooling assessments, and their acknowledgments in media.

4.5. Journalistic investigations: Articles from Wired, The Guardian, Financial Times, Bloomberg, and others that summarize or reveal data (e.g. Google's emission increase, EU AI Act coverage, Crusoe Energy's gas data center).

4.6. Indian market sources: Reports on India's data-center market (e.g. Mercom India, IEEFA, Outlook Business) for domestic capacity and impact estimates.

Quantitative data (e.g. TWh, CO₂, litres) from these sources was synthesised and cross validated the figures (e.g. IEA and Mercom both indicate 1–1.5% global electricity by data centres). Projections (e.g. 2030 demand) are taken from authoritative studies, acknowledging their scenario assumptions. Analysis methods included constructing summary tables of key metrics, and interpreting charts and case figures. For example, Figure 3.1(a) was obtained from an IEA illustration of projected energy demand under different growth scenarios.

While the setup did not employ active water-based cooling, water consumption was calculated indirectly by applying industry-reported WUE factors (e.g., $\sim 1.1 \text{ m}^3$ per MWh for certain climates, as per Google sustainability disclosures) to the measured electricity usage. This allowed estimation of the cooling water footprint in line with hyperscale facility benchmarks, ensuring the dataset remained comparable to real-world AI data centres.

All components are widely available from online marketplaces, require no specialized installation, and can be assembled at home without advanced technical expertise. The setup’s modular nature allows it to be scaled—either by adding more workstations or integrating higher-end GPUs—and replicated across multiple sites, enabling broader data collection for research purposes.

Fig 4.7 (b): SSMS Software’s Code and Real-time Readings

A lightweight Python-based monitoring program was developed to collect and log system resource data during AI workloads. The software integrated with NVIDIA’s NVML library and psutil to record CPU utilization, GPU utilization, power draw, and system temperature. Data was sampled at 5-second intervals and stored in CSV format for later analysis. The monitoring ran for predefined sessions (typically 30–60 minutes per workload), after which the program automatically generated summary statistics (average, peak, and cumulative energy usage) along with basic visualizations (time-series graphs). This ensured reproducibility and consistency across test runs while minimizing manual error.

The software was designed with a minimal GUI for ease of use, allowing the user to: set duration of monitoring; start/stop logging; view live charts of power and temperature; export data to CSV or PNG plots. This approach transformed the laptop into a self-contained monitoring platform without the need for external sensors.

4.8. Direct Industry Data Procurement: To complement our small-scale experimental setup, we proactively reached out to sustainability and data-center operations teams at several leading infrastructure providers—including Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure, AWS, Equinix, and Digital Realty—to request anonymized data on electricity consumption, water usage, and emissions from their AI-intensive facilities. These organizations are widely recognized for their transparent environmental reporting and leadership in green data-center practices. In cases where direct figures were not publicly available, we supplemented our dataset using official disclosures from corporate sustainability reports and centralized platforms such as CDP (the Carbon Disclosure Project) procured conditionally for educational purposes.

V. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Global Energy Demand and Carbon Footprint: Data centres already consume a significant portion of global electricity, and AI is rapidly increasing that share. Current share: IEA and related estimates consistently place data-center electricity use at roughly 1-1.5% of worldwide power (about 240-340 TWh in 2022). This is

similar to some individual countries' electricity use. In 2023 the U.S. data center fleet alone used about 147 TWh ($\approx 3.7\%$ of U.S. demand). Trend: Growth was modest (efficiency offsets) until recently, but the advent of generative AI is driving a surge. IEA projects that by 2030 global data-center demand will climb to ~ 945 TWh (see Fig 3.1 (a)). McKinsey similarly forecasts U.S. data-center use rising to ~ 606 TWh (11.7% of U.S. demand) by 2030.

This boom implies large emissions. In 2020, data centres (with networks) emitted ~ 330 MtCO₂ (0.9% of energy-related emissions). By 2030, if new data-center loads are met by fossil fuels, WattTime estimates U.S. CO₂ could increase by ~ 180 Mt annually. On the other hand, with renewables the emissions could be near zero. Currently, data centres account for $2.5\text{--}3.7\%$ of all global greenhouse gases, a substantial share. The growing share of AI within data centres (from $\sim 20\%$ now to potentially $\sim 50\%$) means AI will increasingly dominate this footprint.

It is worth noting that energy efficiency gains have mitigated demand in past decades. Tech giants report large efficiency improvements: Google claims its data centres are ~ 1.8 times more efficient than the typical enterprise center, with a fleet-average PUE of 1.10 (vs. 1.58 industry). However, Moore's Law gains in chips are slowing, and AI hardware is power-hungry (modern GPUs can draw 700+ W each). As AI workloads become more intense, raw energy demand tends to outpace efficiency gains. In fact, industry reports indicate that even with efficiency, "the money companies pour in to AI" is fuelling unprecedented growth, potentially outstripping past IT expansions.

Case Study—Big Tech: Google and Microsoft have publicly noted the impact of AI on their emissions. Google's sustainability reports (and press coverage) acknowledge that since 2019 its annual GHGs have risen $\sim 48\%$ largely due to increased data-center load for AI and cloud services. Google now warns of "significant uncertainty" in meeting its 2030 net-zero target, explicitly citing AI's unpredictable impact. Microsoft similarly admitted that its 2030 net-zero goal could fall short because of AI-driven demand. These admissions highlight that even companies with massive renewable investments see AI as a material challenge to climate plans.

5.2. The Rise of AI Workloads: Within the broader data-center picture, AI workloads are a rapidly growing subset. De Vries (2025) and others report that AI currently uses about 20% of data-center electricity. If one considers only the incremental power needed to train and run large models (versus baseline IT), AI's share may be larger. Crucially, AI demand is doubling on short time scales: according to Wired, AI's energy demand could double within months, reaching nearly half of data-center power by the end of 2025. This trend is echoed by IEA's data on AI-optimized centres: projected to quadruple by 2030.

Several factors drive this surge: the success of generative AI (ChatGPT, Bard) has spurred worldwide deployment; companies are pursuing "sovereign AI" (country-specific models); and new AI applications are being developed continuously. The Guardian notes that policy shifts (e.g. chip export controls) could temporarily ease hardware demand if supply is constrained. However, companies often double down: for instance, data-center start-up Crusoe Energy is installing 4.5 GW of gas-powered power capacity targeting AI customers like OpenAI. This suggests that to satisfy demand quickly, some AI data centres may rely on fossil generation, at least initially.

In sum, literature indicates AI workloads are now a major driver of data-center growth. Even though efficiency improvements (e.g. model pruning, optimized algorithms) are emerging, their effect may be outweighed by the rapidly expanding scope of AI use.

5.3. Water Usage and Cooling: Energy is only part of the story. Data centres are also huge water consumers, primarily for cooling. Early research by Google's data centres acknowledged that while water-cooling can improve energy efficiency, it creates a large water footprint. In a typical evaporative cooling system, a

significant fraction of cooling water is lost to evaporation. The Lawfare Institute highlights that data centres (and AI specifically) are “water guzzlers” whose growth has increased scarcity pressures. For perspective, a 1 MW facility might use up to 26 million litres of water annually (enough for 62 average U.S. households). With global data-center capacity in the tens of thousands of MW, total water use is enormous (though no global aggregate figure is readily available).

Importantly, AI loads often entail very high-density racks, which can require even more cooling. The IEA note on data centres mentions that cooling-related consumption depends on workload and location. Some data centres (especially HPC/AI) now use “closed-loop” or hybrid cooling to reduce water loss, but many still use open-loop wet cooling with potable or recycled water. Innovations like rear-door heat exchangers and liquid immersion can drastically cut water use, but these are not yet widespread.

Regional example–India. In India’s major data-center hubs (Bengaluru, Mumbai, Chennai, Hyderabad, Pune, NCR), water is already scarce. As of late 2024, Bengaluru’s ~115 MW of data centres withdraw ~8 million litres per day. Water demand from planned expansions (cloud campuses, hyperscale facilities) threatens to exceed local supply. Economic Times reports note that India has no unified policy for data center water use, making regulation lag actual growth. Industry sources warn that without alternative cooling strategies; new Indian data centres could strain city water supplies. (For context, a “midsized” U.S. data center uses ~1.14 ML/day, so Indian centres of tens of MW scale can easily consume millions of litres daily.)

Fig 5.3 (a) shows that AI-optimized data centres consume over 2× more energy, 2–3× more water, and emit significantly higher carbon per unit of compute than traditional facilities, underscoring the steep environmental cost of scaling AI workloads. It can be inferred that AI Optimized Data Centres utilise more resources than Traditional Data Centres at their maximum operation.

Fig 5.3 (a): AI vs Traditional Data Centres: Comparative Intensities

Governments and companies are responding in part. Some proposed data centres in India are incorporating air cooling, dry cooling, or reuse of treated wastewater. Locating centres near coastlines (with abundant seawater for cooling) is being discussed: an IEEFA study notes coastal Mumbai, Chennai and Ahmedabad have thermal conditions favourable for lower cooling needs. But precise data on cooling technologies in India is sparse. Overall, the literature highlights that water use is an urgent but under addressed challenge in AI infrastructure, especially in water-stressed regions.

5.4. India's AI Infrastructure Context: India is rapidly emerging as a key player in global data-center growth, driven by its expanding IT/AI sector and strategic initiatives. Industry analysts estimate India's data-center capacity (across all uses) at ~960 MW in 2023, growing to as much as 9.2 GW by 2030 – nearly a ninefold increase. This growth is partly due to investments by major firms (e.g. Adani Data, Amazon, Google, Microsoft) and supportive policies (e.g. infrastructure status for data centres). Nomura projects that with this expansion, data centres' share of India's electricity could rise from ~0.5% today to ~3% by 2030. In absolute terms, data centres in India consumed ~139 billion kWh in 2023 (~139 TWh), about 2% of the country's power. By comparison, the U.S. figure is ~147 TWh in 2023 (3.7% of U.S. demand).

Several unique factors shape India's context. The majority of India's electricity is coal-based (~60% of generation), so data-center growth there implies high carbon intensity unless mitigated. At 2% of total power today, data centres already add to India's carbon pressure; if unchecked, growth to 3% could complicate national decarbonization targets. On the waterfront, many major metro regions in India face chronic shortages (e.g. Bengaluru, Chennai, Hyderabad). As noted, expected data-center water withdrawals will increase competition for scarce resources, impacting agriculture and households.

India-specific literature calls for sustainable planning of data-center locations and design. For instance, Outlook Business and IEEFA recommend siting facilities near renewable-energy zones and abundant cooling sources, to minimize the need for fossil power and potable water. Indian regulators have begun imposing water-use norms and encouraging "green" certification for data centres, but enforcement is uneven. Given India's projected ninefold capacity growth, proactive policy (national water guidelines, mandatory efficiency standards) will be crucial. In summary, India exemplifies the global AI trend: rapid data-center build-out in emerging markets, with acute energy and water sustainability challenges.

5.5. Continued AI model scaling: If model sizes grow (e.g. GPT-4 to GPT-5) and multi-modal AI expands, per-model training costs may rise. However, there is also a possibility of efficiency breakthroughs (e.g. sparsity techniques, better chip architectures) that could reduce energy per computation. Early evidence (like DeepSeek's claims) shows potential for major efficiency gains. But overall compute demand is predicted to continue climbing for the foreseeable future.

5.6. Decarbonization of grids: Many scenarios assume grids will become greener. The IEA's "Net Zero by 2050" trajectory implies that by 2030 most new power is renewable. If that materializes, the same TWh demand would emit much less CO₂ than today. Conversely, if fossil-intensive sources (especially new gas plants) dominate data-center expansion, emissions will remain high. Power source choices are the most significant determinant of ultimate emissions.

5.7. Geopolitical and economic factors: Influence data-center placement, for example, India's datacentre boom is partly driven by government incentives and demand for data sovereignty. Similar trends (e.g. Africa's emergence) could shift where growth happens, with implications for local power and water constraints. Export controls on chips (as seen for Chinese tech) could also change compute geography.

5.8. Technology shifts: Emerging technologies like 5nm and beyond chips, photonic computing, and even quantum computing could alter energy profiles. Quantum, if it becomes practical, might offer orders-of-magnitude compute-per-energy, but that is speculative. In the near term, continued GPU advancements (e.g. 800+ W GPUs) further stress cooling, but also enable faster training (so total hours and thus energy might rise or fall depending on use patterns).

Given these uncertainties, our analysis highlights the critical need for ongoing monitoring and adaptation. Data transparency (power and water use metrics) should be improved so that trends can be tracked. Research into energy-efficient AI (sometimes called “Green AI”) is needed to ensure that innovation does not ignore environmental costs. Otherwise, unchecked growth risks overwhelming improvement efforts.

VI. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

From the synthesis above, key findings include:

6.1. Rapid growth in AI-driven energy demand: Global data-center electricity consumption is on track to roughly double by 2030. AI-specific workloads are a major part of this surge, potentially constituting nearly half of data-center power by 2025. In the U.S., data centres may approach 10–12% of power demand by 2030.

6.2. Substantial carbon footprint: Presently, data centres (including AI) account for ~2.5–3.7% of global GHG emissions. If new AI data centres are powered by fossil fuels, emissions could jump by tens to hundreds of millions of tonnes CO₂ annually. In India, where grid emission factors are high, the planned 9 times growth in data centres could significantly raise national CO₂ if not paired with clean energy.

6.3. Water stress concerns: Data centres use vast quantities of cooling water. A 1 MW facility may use ~26 million litres/year. In water-stressed regions (e.g. Bengaluru), data centres are already consuming millions of litres per day. Without intervention, new AI data centres in urban India and elsewhere will strain municipal water supplies.

Fig 6.3 (a): AI Data Centre Hubs and Regional Water Stress Levels

This world map overlays major AI data center hubs (black dots) with regional water stress levels (red = extreme, orange = high, blue = low). The map highlights that many fast-growing AI clusters—such as Bengaluru, Chennai, Hyderabad, and Dubai—are concentrated in high water-stress regions, where cooling needs to heighten competition with local communities. In contrast, hubs in Germany, Canada, and Brazil align with low-stress zones, underscoring how site selection strongly shapes the sustainability of AI infrastructure.

6.4. Current mitigation offers only partial relief: Technologies like liquid immersion or cold-plate cooling can cut data-center energy use ~15–20% and water use ~30–50%. Renewable energy sourcing can virtually

eliminate new operational emissions. However, these alone may not offset overall growth. For instance, even if Google’s data centres reach 100% renewable, expanding capacity still increases total power drawn. Immersion cooling faces challenges (PFAS fluids) and is not yet widespread. Dry cooling can save water, but may raise PUE. Thus, while existing solutions help, they must be scaled and combined with demand management.

6.5. Case-study insights: Google and Microsoft demonstrate that even best-in-class data centres see rising footprints with AI. OpenAI/Microsoft’s Stargate project illustrates how scale-up can drive investments in new (often gas-based) plants. These examples underline that corporate emissions commitments can be undermined by surging AI load.

6.6. India’s context: India’s data-center expansion is on a global scale relative to its grid. Data centres today already consume ~2% of India’s electricity; projections to ~3% by 2030 imply hundreds of TWh of demand and significant emissions if coal-sourced. The combination of high coal reliance and local water scarcity makes sustainability more difficult. However, India also has abundant solar potential and monsoon season (for pumped hydro storage), which could be harnessed if planned in tandem.

Metric	Current Value	Projections
Global DC electricity consumption	~240–340 TWh (1–1.5% of global-2022)	~945 TWh (≈8% global) by 2030
Data centres’ share of global GHG	~2.5–3.7%	Would remain ~2–3% if demand decarbonizes; higher if not
AI share of data-center power	~20% in 2024	~40–50% by end-2025
India DC capacity	~960 MW (2023)	Up to ~9.2 GW (×9) by 2030
India DC electricity share	~0.5% of national grid (2023)	Up to ~3% by 2030
Global data-center water use	No consolidated global tally; 1 MW uses ~26 ML/year	Likely to rise commensurate with energy growth
Bengaluru DC water use (115 MW)	~8 million litres/day	Increase as capacity grows (no data yet)
Google’s GHG rise (2019–2024)	+48%, driven by AI infrastructure	–
Microsoft immersion cooling benefit	–	Cuts GHG 15–21%, energy 15–20%, water 31–52% vs air-cooling

Table. 6.6 (a): Key Data Center/AI Infrastructure metrics and Projections (from IEA, LBNL, and others)

Overall, the findings confirm that AI infrastructure imposes significant environmental costs under current practices, and that these costs are set to escalate unless mitigated. Importantly, the gap between business-as-usual growth and sustainable pathways is large: even aggressive efficiency gains may fall short if AI demand quadruples.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis, comparison of technologies we make the following recommendations (technical recommendations are strictly constrained to use of new ways of adaption of emerging technologies or already underused existing technology) for industry stakeholders and policymakers:

7.1. Accelerate renewable energy integration: AI data centres should be paired with carbon-free power sources. This means prioritizing 24/7 matching (as Google aims) and making new data-center projects contingent on dedicated renewable capacity or grid decarbonization plans. Governments can facilitate this by streamlining permitting for renewable PPAs and grid upgrades near data centres. In India, this implies fast-tracking solar/wind projects near major data-center hubs, and incentivizing hybrid storage (to balance variability).

7.2. Mandate energy and water transparency: Regulators should require data-center operators to report annual electricity and water use (both direct and “embodied” where possible). Mandatory disclosure, as in the EU AI Act for model energy use, creates accountability. Standardized metrics (Power Usage Effectiveness, Water Usage Effectiveness) should be publicly filed, enabling comparison and benchmarking. This transparency will spur competition on efficiency and inform policy (e.g. placing limits on data-center density in stressed regions).

7.3. Encourage adoption of advanced cooling: Industry should adopt low-water/low-energy cooling for AI-grade centres. For new builds, immersion or rear-door cooling (with dry or hybrid loops) should be prioritized, especially in water-scarce areas. Governments can offer tax credits or fast-track approval for green-cooled facilities. Public research funding (e.g. DOE programs) should support development of non-toxic immersion fluids (PFAS alternatives) to address regulatory hurdles.

7.4. Leverage waste heat: Wherever feasible, data-center heat should be captured for district heating or industrial processes. Urban planning should reserve land and infrastructure (e.g. piping) for heat reuse near data centres. Pilot projects (e.g. heating housing, greenhouses, or desalination plants) can demonstrate viability. Although seasonal temperate climates are easiest, even tropical regions could use waste heat for cooling chiller pre-cooling or aquaculture.

7.5. Plan sustainable siting: Data-center location decisions must weigh resource constraints. Avoid siting new large centres in water-stressed basins or coal-heavy grid regions unless accompanied by offsetting measures. Zoning policies can promote data-center campuses in areas with renewable potential (sun/wind), cooler climates, or access to water recycling. In India, for example, encouraging clusters along Kerala/Tamil Nadu coasts (with abundant hydro or marine cooling) may be preferable to inland thermal-only locations.

7.6. Invest in chip and software efficiency: Tech companies and researchers should continue R&D into energy-efficient AI. This includes chip-level innovations (more efficient AI accelerators), and algorithmic efficiency (model pruning, quantization). Funding “Green AI” initiatives (such as the European Green Software Foundation) can yield breakthroughs that reduce compute needs. At the same time, training models in carbon-friendly locations/time periods (as part of lifecycle strategy) can cut footprint.

7.7. Adopt circular economy principles: The industry should ensure long lifetimes, reuse, and recycling of servers and components. Extended producer responsibility or take-back programs can recover precious metals and reduce e-waste. This is an emerging area in the literature but worth stressing.

7.8. International cooperation and standards: Given the global nature of AI, international bodies (IEA, ITU, ISO) should develop guidelines for sustainable AI infrastructure. Frameworks like the Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact (EU) could be adapted worldwide. Tech companies should collaborate on open benchmarking (similar to the Hardware Efficiency Accelerator project) to share best practices.

Implementing these measures is challenging but essential. No single solution suffices; rather a portfolio of actions—technological, policy, and corporate—must be pursued aggressively. Otherwise, the findings suggest the AI infrastructure could lock in a new wave of emissions and resource strain, undermining climate and sustainability goals.

VIII. DESIGN OPTIMIZATION SOLUTIONS

8.1. Rationale and Objective: Findings in this study indicate that AI-intensive facilities face a three-way constraint—cooling energy, freshwater withdrawals, and carbon intensity—that current single-mode designs do not jointly optimize. The Climate-Adaptive Data Center Design (CADCD) is proposed as an integrated (overcoming no single solution sufficiency), original framework that co-optimizes architectural orientation, aerodynamic intake innovation, hardware, adaptive cooling, and sustainable operations to lower total environmental externalities without compromising AI rack densities or service-level objectives.

8.2. Core Design Concept: CADCD will consist of three tightly coupled layers that operate from site planning through real-time control:

8.2.1. Passive Orientation & Envelope Optimization of Data Centres (Design Layer):

1. *Orientation and massing;* Align server halls on a north–south axis to limit direct solar gain on façades; use elongated floorplates to promote laminar inflow and short, contained hot-aisle exhaust paths.
2. *High-albedo and shading strategies;* Specify reflective roofs, dynamic external shading (louvers/brise-soleil), and low-emissivity glazing only where necessary to minimize incident heat.
3. *Wind-assisted intake and stack effects;* Sculpt intake façades and rooftop exhaust stacks/clerestories to exploit prevailing winds and buoyancy for passive pressure differentials, reducing fan work.
4. *Thermal buffering;* Incorporate green façades, light-coloured pavements, and localized earth-coupling/geothermal pre-conditioning (where feasible) to depress inlet air temperatures.
5. *Containment and layout;* Use sealed hot-aisle containment, short plenums, and rack zoning that groups high-density AI racks nearest liquid headers.
6. *Bluff-body aerodynamic intakes:* A novel feature that places flat-plate, high-drag structures in front of cold-aisle intakes. Unlike streamlined vents, these intentionally generate drag and turbulence, creating a pressure zone that captures and forces more air into server racks. This enhances airflow without additional fan power, extends the viability of air-side economization, and lowers overall cooling energy.

Fig. 8.2 (a): CADCD Bluff-Body Rack Intake & Aero-shape Analysis

8.2.2. Adaptive Cooling Infrastructure (ACI) (Hardware Layer):

1. Multi-mode topology; Engineer a plant that can switch among:
 - Dry air economization (air-side or indirect, no water) when ambient/wet-bulb allows.
 - Closed-loop liquid/cold-plate cooling for >30–80 kW/rack AI densities.
 - Rear-door heat exchangers for transitional loads and legacy rows.
 - Heat-recovery mode via plate exchangers to feed district heating or adjacent process loads.
2. Manifold and valving; Provide headered supply/return manifolds with automated valves and VFD-controlled pumps/fans that enable rapid, loss-minimized transitions between modes.
3. Sensing and telemetry; Instrument racks and plant with IT load, inlet/outlet temps, ΔP , humidity, and flow sensors at high temporal resolution to support control stability.

8.2.3. Carbon- and Water-Aware Orchestrator (CWAO) (Operations Layer):

1. *Decision inputs*: Real-time wet-bulb temperature, grid carbon intensity, water budget, IT queue/SLA, and thermal headroom.
2. *Control Objective*: Minimize a composite cost $J = w_1 \cdot (\text{cooling kWh}) + w_2 \cdot (\text{water L}) + w_3 \cdot (\text{kg CO}_2\text{e})$ where w_1, w_2, w_3 are weighting factors set by site priorities. subject to SLA and thermal constraints.
3. *Scheduling policy*: Training jobs with flexibility are shifted to periods with lower grid carbon intensity and favourable ambient conditions (enabling dry or liquid-closed-loop operation). Inference and latency-critical loads remain pinned but benefit from dynamic mode selection.
4. *Mode-selection logic (conceptual)*: If wet-bulb \leq threshold \rightarrow prioritize dry economization. Else if rack power \geq density threshold \rightarrow closed-loop liquid; enable heat recovery when ΔT is sufficient. If site water budget tight \rightarrow hard-limit evaporative assists; otherwise allow limited adiabatic boost within budget.

Fig. 8.2 (b): CWAO Breakdown (Water-efficient LLM Data, Credit: AM Library)

Climate Adaptive Data Centre Design (CADCD)

Fig. 8.2 (c): Climate Adaptive Data Centre Design - CADCD Breakdown

8.3. Implementation Roadmap: The following phases can be followed/implemented to build a CADCD that suits the location, and later on scale it accordingly.

1. *Phase 1: Siting and Climate Screening.* Use multi-criteria screening (renewable proximity, water-stress indices, ambient temperature/humidity profiles) to select or rate sites; prefer locations enabling high economization hours and low water stress.
2. *Phase 2: Design Integration.* Embed CADCD features in architectural drawings and MEP schematics: orientation, shading, manifolds, liquid readiness, and heat-recovery interconnects.
3. *Phase 3: Controls and Telemetry.* Deploy a digital twin of the plant for controller tuning; integrate grid-carbon and weather feeds; define water budgets and SLA-aware job classes.
4. *Phase 4: Pilot and Scale.* Commission a pilot row (e.g., one hot aisle) with liquid readiness and switching logic; validate against matched control conditions, then scale to additional rows/halls.
5. *Phase 5: Key Performance Indicators (for Verification);*
 - PUE (Power Usage Effectiveness), WUE (Water Usage Effectiveness), and CUE (Carbon Usage Effectiveness).
 - Annualized water avoided (m³) versus evaporative baseline.
 - Cooling energy reduction (kWh) and economization hours (% of year).
 - Heat-recovery utilization (MWh exported) and avoided scope-2/3 emissions at sink.
 - Workload shifting rate (% of training compute executed in low-carbon, low-water windows).
 - SLA compliance (latency/throughput) and thermal compliance (inlet temperature excursions).

8.4. Illustrative Benefits: (Scenario-Based, To Be Quantified in Future Work)

1. Under representative climates, CADCD is expected to:
2. Reduce annualized water withdrawals by prioritizing dry and closed-loop modes, using adiabatic assists only within preset budgets.
3. Lower cooling electricity by exploiting night-time and shoulder-season economization and right-sizing fan/pump work through pressure control.
4. Support higher AI rack densities with cold-plate paths, avoiding the airflow penalties of all-air systems.

5. Create a heat-recovery asset that can offset local heating fuel consumption and partially monetize waste heat.

8.5. Potential Risks, Trade-offs, and Mitigations:

1. *Controls complexity*: Multi-mode switching increases control-system sophistication; mitigate via digital-twin tuning, conservative fallback states, and rigorous alarms.
2. *Capex and integration*: Additional headers/valves and liquid readiness raise capex; mitigate through modularization (row-by-row rollout) and retrofit kits for legacy halls.
3. *Operational risk (leaks/fluids)*: Use dielectric fluids where immersion is adopted; implement double-containment and drip detection; define fluid maintenance protocols.
4. *Site dependence*: Benefits vary with climate and grid mix; address via site-specific parameterization and publishing measured KPIs post-commissioning.

8.6. Economic Rationale (High-Level):

1. OpEx savings from reduced fan/pump energy and minimized water purchases/treatment.
2. Revenue or avoided cost from waste-heat offtake agreements (district heating, industrial processes, aquaculture, greenhouse farming).
3. Resilience value via diversified cooling modes (maintaining capacity during heat waves or water restrictions).
4. Future-proofing for tightening environmental standards and ESG disclosure requirements.

IX. CONCLUSION

The growth of AI is a double-edged sword for society's future: while it promises innovation and productivity, it carries hidden environmental costs in its infrastructure. This paper has assessed those costs comprehensively. Our review shows that current AI-capable data centres are driving up global electricity demand and emissions, and placing heavy demand on water resources, especially in emerging economies like India. Without intervention, AI may threaten to turn data centres into a major climate liability.

However, the analysis also uncovers clear pathways to mitigation. Efficiency gains and clean energy can greatly reduce per-unit impacts, and new cooling and reuse strategies can alleviate resource strains. Crucially, all stakeholders must act in concert: industry must invest in sustainable designs, governments must enforce smart regulations, and researchers must innovate further. The imperative is to decouple AI's computational growth from carbon and water footprints. If data centres become fully powered by renewables, use water judiciously, and recycle waste heat, AI can continue to expand without proportionally expanding its ecological footprint. That will require aggressive targets and follow-through – for example, Google's 24/7 carbon-free goal by 2030 is a model of the ambition needed.

In conclusion, the "true cost of AI infrastructure" is high under business-as-usual, but not immutable. With foresight and commitment, the AI industry can achieve its advancements in a sustainable manner. The analyses here highlight both the scale of the challenge and the scope of solutions. Policymakers and companies should heed these findings to ensure that the AI revolution does not outpace our planet's limits.

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